

The Karun Reservoir benchmark case modelled with RTC-Tools

Supplementary material to Ponnambalam et al. (2025)

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1 Generic model

1.1 Hydraulic model

The storage equation relates the change in the volume in the reservoir against the incoming and outgoing flows, Q_{in} and Q_{out} respectively:

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = Q_{\text{in}} - Q_{\text{out}} \quad (1)$$

The outgoing flow from the reservoir is distributed between the turbines and the spill flow

$$Q_{\text{out}} = Q_{\text{turbine}} + Q_{\text{spill}} \quad (2)$$

where spill flow accounts for the flow that is not used for power generation, i. e. flow through the spillway and the flow through the bottom outlet if a bottom outlet is present.

The volume and water level H of the reservoir lake (the reservoir storage) are related to each other by a strictly monotonically increasing function that accounts for the shape of the basin:

$$H = f(V) \quad (3)$$

Such function is usually non-linear and in practice often specified as a table or a polynomial function. Usually, the relation between H and V is not linear.

The hydropower generation P is a function of the turbine flow and the head difference:

$$P = \Delta h \cdot Q_{\text{turbine}} \cdot \eta \cdot \rho \cdot g \quad (4)$$

with the turbine efficiency η , the density of water ρ and the gravity constant g . The head difference Δh is defined as

$$\Delta h = H - h_{\text{tailwater}} \quad (5)$$

The tailwater level $h_{\text{tailwater}}$ is expressed in dependence of the reservoir outflow Q_{out} :

$$h_{\text{tailwater}} = f(Q_{\text{out}}). \quad (6)$$

Δh usually decreases as Q_{out} increases, because the outflow from the reservoir decreases the water level H in the reservoir and possibly increases the tailwater $h_{\text{tailwater}}$. Therefore, meeting a power generation target is a non-trivial interplay between Δh and Q_{out} .

We are interested in an optimal release scheme over a certain time horizon. The storage equation 1 is discretized in time with the help of timesteps $j = 1 \dots J$ and becomes

$$\frac{V_j - V_{j-1}}{\Delta t} - (Q_{in,j} - Q_{out,j}) = 0 \quad (7)$$

1.2 Operational goals

Reservoirs have one or more purposes and are operated to meet objectives like flood control, recreation, hydropower production or drinking water supply. As an operational goal we understand here the mathematical formulation of an objective that the operators aim to meet with the help of reservoir control. Goals are terms of the objective function in a mathematical optimization problem, also referred to as soft constraints.

Objectives can conflict with each other, and not all goals are met all the times. An example for conflicting goals are hydropower production and flood protection. From a flood protection point of view, the water level should be as low as possible, because this provides storage room to catch water from a flood wave in the reservoir and reduce the peak discharge further downstream. For hydropower production, however, the water level should be high at all times, because a high reservoir stage means more hydropower output with the same turbine flow. Optimization of reservoir operations means to find a reservoir release pattern such that multiple goals are met as good as possible. In the following we present a selection of typical objectives for reservoir operations and the related mathematical formulation as optimization goals.

An operational range for the reservoir water level can be translated to an operational volume range V_{\min} and V_{\max} with the help of Equation 3. The mathematical formulation of an operational volume range goal reads:

$$\text{minimize } V_j - V_{j,\max} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{minimize } V_{j,\min} - V_j \quad (9)$$

The operational range can be specified for one or multiple time steps j in the time horizon J . Typically, an operational range for the reservoir water level is a general goal that applies as a guidance for daily operations and is only exceeded in special situations like flood or drought conditions.

Accordingly, a range goal for the reservoir outflow Q_{out} is defined as

$$\text{minimize } Q_{out,j} - Q_{out,j,\max} \quad (10)$$

$$\text{minimize } Q_{out,j,\min} - Q_{out,j} \quad (11)$$

and for power generation

$$\text{minimize } P_j - P_{j,\max} \quad (12)$$

$$\text{minimize } P_{j,\min} - P_j \quad (13)$$

To maximize the hydropower production a maximization goal at all time steps j applies:

$$\text{maximize } P_j \quad (14)$$

1.3 Constraints and bounds

While goals not necessarily have to be satisfied, constraints must be obeyed at all times. Constraints define the solution space for the optimization problem. If no solution exists that complies with all constraints, the optimization problem is infeasible. Constraints in this closer mathematical sense are called hard constraints to distinguish them from soft constraints (see Sec. 1.2).

The first group of constraints is given by the water system equations in Section 1.1. Governing equations of the water system model are typically equality constraints.

The second group of constraints are so-called bounds. Bounds constrain the range of state variables — the optimization variables or variables derived from them. Typically, bounds are inequality constraints that represent physical limits with values for a specific site. Typically, the minimum and maximum volume V_{\min} and V_{\max} in a reservoir, the discharge capacity of a turbine $Q_{\text{turbine,max}}$, the capacity of bottom outlet and the spillway $Q_{\text{spill,max}}$, generator limits or grid capacity P_{\max} are implemented as bounds:

$$V_{\min} \leq V_j \leq V_{\max} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (15)$$

$$Q_{\text{out,min}} \leq Q_{j,\text{out}} \leq Q_{\text{out,max}} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (16)$$

$$Q_{j,\text{spill}} \leq Q_{\text{spill,max}} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (17)$$

$$Q_{\text{turbine,min}} \leq Q_{j,\text{turbine}} \leq Q_{\text{turbine,max}} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (18)$$

$$P_j \leq P_{\max} \quad \forall j \in J \quad (19)$$

1.4 Optimization problem

In general, an optimization problem reads:

$$\text{minimize } f(x) \quad (20)$$

subject to:

$$g_1(x) \leq 0 \quad (21)$$

$$g_2(x) = 0 \quad (22)$$

where $f(x)$ is the objective function, x is the optimization variable, and g_1 and g_2 are inequality constraints and equality constraints, respectively.

If f and g_1 are convex and g_2 is affine, i.e. can be formulated as $g_2 = ax + b$ (linear), the optimization problem is called convex. In convex optimization problems any local optimal solution is also globally optimal. As mentioned above, the global optimum is required for stable optimization results, which is considered an important prerequisite for the usage of optimization within an operational water management context.

The optimization problems of this study are composed by equality constraints given with the hydraulic model equations from Section 1.1, objective function terms formulated as goals as described in Section 1.2 and bounds according to Section 1.3 as inequality constraints.

As long as only reservoir volume and flows are concerned, the optimization problem is linear, and consequently can be solved to a global optimum.

The the hydropower equation (Eq. 4) contains the product of two variables Q_{turbine} and Δh . This makes the problem nonlinear. If the optimization goal is to maximize power, the optimization problem remains convex and still can be solved to a global optimum.

When adding further non-linear components to the optimization problem with the relation between water level and reservoir volume (Eq. 3) and the tailwater equation (Eq. 6), the problem is no longer convex.

With the homotopy method such optimization problem can be solved to a path-stable solution. The homotopy method, a path-stable non-linear optimization with a dynamic formulation for the head difference and a non-linear relation between reservoir volume and reservoir water level.

1.5 Implementation in a generic modelling software

RTC-Tools 2 (Deltares 2019; Schwanenberg et al. 2015) is a generic modelling software for the optimization of water systems. An RTC-Tools model consists of

- A hydraulic layer that contains the flow equations for the water system, related equations and bounds,
- A control layer with the operational goals,
- The data layer to manage input time series, model parameters and model output.

The hydraulic model is written in the Modelica modelling language. RTC-Tools provides a Modelica library with water-related equations to model reservoirs, river segments etc. Sections 1.1 and 1.3 contain the equations for reservoir modelling. The user can build water system models with these generic building blocks.

The control model must be scripted in Python. RTC-Tools offers two approaches to handle competing goals and objectives within the optimization:

- Multi-objective optimization (Pareto-optimization), where goals are traded off against each other. Weighting factors can be assigned to the goals in order to control the trade-off. Multi-objective optimization applies where different goals must be balanced with each other to achieve a compromise.
- Lexicographic goal programming (Eschenbach et al. 2001), where goals are arranged in an ordered list. This list is then worked down step by step, making sure that when optimizing a goal, the previously optimized goals are still met. Lexicographic goal programming is a natural fit to systems where goals have clearly defined priorities, such as safety concerns (e.g. flood control) taking precedence over economic optimization (e.g. hydropower production).

The data layer is a set of input files in comma separated value format (CSV). RTC-Tools also supports the FEWS-PI file format for integration in operational decision support systems based on the Delft-FEWS platform (Werner et al. 2013).

The RTC-Tools computational core is written in Python and compiles the three layers into an optimization problem and feeds it to a solver. The interior point optimizer IPOPT (Wächter and Biegler 2006) and HiGHS (Huangfu and Hall 2018) have been used for this study. Other solvers, like the mixed integer COIN Branch and Cut Solver CBC (Forrest et al. 2018), are also available.

This software solution falls into the category of exact mathematical optimization according to Becker et al. (2024).

2 Case study

2.1 The schematization

The schematization of the water system consists of three nodes (Fig. 1 from left to right): an inflow boundary condition, the reservoir node which basically represents the reservoir equation

1, and a terminal for the downstream boundary.

Figure 1: Model schematization (Open Modelica Connection Editor)

2.1.1 Goals

Table 1: Goals

State	goal type	Minimum	Maximum	Priority	Description
V	range	$1449 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$	$2232 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$	1	outer volume range
Q_{out}	range	time series	—	3	minimum release
P	range	time series	—	4	minimum power generation
V	range	time series	—	2	minimum volume at last time step
P	maximization	n. a.	n. a.	6	maximize power generation

The operational objectives listed in Table 1 are optimized for with goal programming (Section 1.5).

2.2 The linear model

2.2.1 Water system model: equations und bounds

The linear model uses a linear model equation for the relation between water level and volume (Eq. 3) with

$$\bar{H} = a \cdot V + b \quad (23)$$

where \bar{H} is the linearised water level in the reservoir and a and b are reservoir-dependent parameters.

The tailwater equation (Eq. 6) is used in a linear form, too:

$$\bar{h}_{\text{tailwater}} = \alpha \cdot Q_{\text{out}} + \beta \quad (24)$$

Here, α and β being reservoir-dependent parameters.

Consequently, the head difference (5) computed with reservoir water level \bar{H} and $h_{\text{tailwater}}$ becomes

$$\Delta \bar{h} = \bar{H} - \bar{h}_{\text{tailwater}} \quad (25)$$

The power equation then becomes

$$\bar{P} = \Delta \bar{h} \cdot Q_{\text{turbine}} \cdot \eta \cdot \rho \cdot g. \quad (26)$$

Table 2: Parameters of the linear model

Parameter	Value
a	0.03862/1 000 000
b	942.5018707
α	0.0071
β	840.3
η	0.89

Equations (1) (2), 23, 24, 25 and Equation 26 form the equality constraints of the optimization model. Parameters are given in Table 2.

Bounds are given in Table 3. The table also contains a nominal value which is used to scale the state variables against each other.

Table 3: Bounds of the linear model and nominal values

State variable	Minimum value	Maximum value	Nominal value
V	0	2 901 600 000 m ³	2 173 140 000 m ³
Q_{out}	0 m ³ /s	1800 m ³ /s	1000 m ³ /s
P	-0.01	1065 MW	800 MW

To account for the dependency of turbine discharge from the filling level a set of linear inequality constraints is applied:

$$Q_{\text{turbine}} - m_k(V - V_k) - Q_{\text{turbine},k} \leq 0 \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (27)$$

Parameters for V_k , $Q_{\text{turbine},k}$ and m_k are given in Table 4, where the slope m_k is calculated as

$$m_k = \frac{Q_{\text{turbine},k+1} - Q_{\text{turbine},k}}{V_{k+1} - V_k} \quad k = 1, 2, 3 \quad (28)$$

Table 4: Parameters for constraints to account for the dependency of turbine flow on water volume in the reservoir

k	Elevation (m)	Volume V_k (10 ⁶ m ³)	$Q_{\text{turbine},k}$ (m ³ /s)	m_k
1	998	1449.4	150	6.6098857101
2	1001	1518.085	604	0.2279202279
3	1009	1711.135	648	-0.1458887215
4	1028	2232.08	571	

2.2.2 Results

The optimization results for all goals (Table 1) solved in a sequence is shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows how the solution develops during the goal programming procedure. The maximize power generation goal is applied as last goal, not before all the other goals are satisfied as good as possible. After optimizing until the first priority the requirements for minimum flow and

minimum power generation are not yet met. The request for minimum volume at the last time step only affects the last portion of the modelling period.

Figure 2: Optimization results

Figure 3: Intermediate optimization results after each priority

2.3 The nonlinear model with continuation method

2.3.1 The continuation method

The basic idea of the continuation method (also referred to as homotopy method, Becker et al. (2023)) is a continuous (i. e., homotopic) deformation of the optimization problem from a linear problem to a non-linear one. The use of homotopy for addressing non-linearities in water system optimization has been developed by Baayen et al. (2018a, 2020) and has been applied for different water-related optimization problems (Baayen et al. 2019, 2018b; Becker et al. 2023). The mathematical background for the application of the homotopy method for the hydropower equation is documented in Baayen et al. (2018c) and Becker et al. (2023).

Solving a non-linear non-convex optimization problem directly can lead to stability issues, because a non-linear non-convex problem can have multiple local solutions. Under some mild technical conditions, a non-linear solver guarantees to find one of such minima (Baayen et al. 2018c). To solve a non-linear optimization problem, a gradient-descent algorithms needs a starting point. In principle, and in practise, providing two even very close starting points can lead to different local optima. This becomes problematic in an operational context where it is important for the final solution to be robust to small perturbations. By starting the optimization with the linear problem, the continuation method provides a way to find a stable (or 'reliable') starting point for the solution of the full non-linear equations in the end.

To facilitate the deformation of the optimization problem from linear to non-linear, each non-linear equation is expressed as a linear combination of its non-linear representation and its linear approximation, where the non-linear equation is what we want to solve for. A parameter Θ takes values from 0 to 1 to move from the linear to the non-linear formulation. The relation between water level and volume in the reservoir becomes:

$$\frac{V}{1\,000\,000} = (1-\Theta) \underbrace{(25.84436275 \cdot H - 24355.37745)}_{\text{linear part}} + \Theta \underbrace{(c_5 \cdot H^5 + c_4 \cdot H^4 + c_3 \cdot H^3 + c_2 \cdot H^2 + c_1 \cdot H + c_0)}_{\text{nonlinear part}} \quad (29)$$

The relation for tailwater level becomes:

$$h_{\text{tailwater}} = (1-\Theta) \underbrace{(0.0071 \cdot Q_{\text{out}} + 840.3)}_{\text{linear part}} + \Theta \underbrace{(-5.42242 \times 10^{-6} \cdot Q_{\text{out}}^2 + 0.0112481 \cdot Q_{\text{out}} + 839.9016)}_{\text{nonlinear part}} \quad (30)$$

Table 5: Polynomial coefficients for the relation between water level and volume

Coefficient	Value
c_5	0
c_4	-2.90458E-08
c_3	0.000149542
c_2	-0.154744081
c_1	0
c_0	35742.85351

If $\Theta = 0$, the linearised equation between water level and volume is obtained, with $\Theta = 1$, one obtains the desired non-linear equation for the relation between water level and volume and the tailwater level.

The homotopic deformation is basically a sequence of multiple continuous non-linear optimization problems, here solved with the Interior Point Optimizer IPOPT (Wächter and Biegler 2006). A homotopy optimization starts with a full optimization run with $\Theta = 0$. Full optimization run means here that all goals and constraints are included. With $\Theta = 0$ only the linear part the homotopy formulation (Eq. 29) is active. The optimization problem can be solved to a global optimum. The solution of this first optimization run is now set as seeding for a consecutive optimization where Θ is increased by an increment of $\Delta\Theta$ to a value larger than zero. This second optimization problem has now a small non-linear component, but it is still similar to the first, linear optimization problem. With the seeding being the result from a similar optimization problem, the solution of the second optimization problem is found quickly. This procedure is repeated until Θ has reached 1, now the optimization problem with the desired non-linear equations is solved. Since the linear problem has a unique solution and each deformation only slightly changes the problem, this method provides a reliable way to find a ‘good’ starting point for the fully non-linear problem. Note that the homotopy method ensures a stable optimization result but does not come with a guarantee for a global optimum for the non-linear optimization problem. The solution is always connected to the global optimum of the corresponding linear problem, though.

A typical value for $\Delta\Theta$ is 0.1, this is the value that has also been used for this study. Larger values of $\Delta\Theta$ can be chosen, too, for example $\Delta\Theta = 0.2$ or $\Delta\Theta = 0.5$. With large values for $\Delta\Theta$ it can happen that the optimization fails. Our implementation of the homotopy method (see Section 1.5) repeats the optimization run with $\frac{1}{2}\Delta\Theta$ in this case. Beside $\Delta\Theta$ the user specifies $\Delta\Theta_{\min}$ to limit the automatic reduction of $\Delta\Theta$.

The advantage of the homotopy method is that the optimization applies the desired non-linear formulation, meaning that the equations are not simplified. In the power generation the full interplay between Δh and Q_{turbine} is captured (Becker et al. 2023).

3 Computing times

The computing time for the two models is shown in Table 6. Optimization runs were carried out on a HP EliteBook 830 with a processor 12th Gen Intel Core i5-1235U, 1300 MHz under Windows 11 operating system with RTC-Tools 2.7.0 under Python 3.13. The computing time includes input file reading and output file writing and initialization; result plotting is not included in the computing time.

Table 6: Computing Times

Model variant	Computing time
Linear model with IPOPT	0:00:10.477508
Linear model with HiGHS	0:00:00.887677
Nonlinear model with IPOPT	0:00:37.276018

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